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Predicting Coastal Dissolved Oxygen Values with the Use of Artificial Neural Networks: A Case Study for Cyprus

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Abstract. Coastal hypoxia is a serious environmental problem that needs to be addressed at a global level. The phenomenon of hypoxia is characterized by low Dissolved Oxygen (DO) levels in the water column that causes detrimental effects on aquatic organisms. Anthropogenic activities such as intensive agriculture practices and point-source nutrient loading are considered the main causes of coastal hypoxia. This study utilizes data-driven modelling based on Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), and specifically Feed-Forward ANNs, to predict surface DO levels. Several surface water quality parameters such as water temperature, nitrogen species (ammonium, nitrite and nitrate), phosphorus, pH, salinity, electrical conductivity, and chlorophyll-a served as the ANN's input parameters. These parameters were measured at several sampling sites in the coastal waters of Cyprus and some of the sites were located near areas with anthropogenic activities, during the period 2000-2021. An ANN with a 9-5-1 topology was developed and ANN managed to predict with good accuracy the DO levels, with the Coefficient of determination (r^2) as high as $r^2=0.991$ for the test set. Additionally, sensitivity analysis was performed to measure the impact of each input parameter on the DO level, and it was estimated that the water temperature is the most influential factor. The "Weights" sensitivity analysis algorithm was used for this purpose. The ANN-based method proposed can be used as a management tool for predicting the DO levels and prevention of hypoxia. Therefore, this work has a positive impact on marine sciences and marine information technology.

1. Introduction

Coastal water pollution management is essential as coastal waters are major providers of economical services (e.g., tourist activities, aquaculture). Eutrophication and the closely associated phenomenon of hypoxia (low levels of dissolved oxygen (DO)) are two serious threats facing water bodies worldwide [1]. Such threats can significantly affect Mediterranean countries such as Cyprus that depend on tourism and related aquatic leisure activities (e.g., swimming, sailing) but also emerging sectors such as aquaculture [2]. One of the requirements of the Republic of Cyprus as a member state of the European Union (EU) is to achieve and maintain Good Environmental status (GES) of the marine waters according to the requirements of the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive 2008/56/EC and the Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC. As it is stated by Best et al. [3] under the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD), the DO is one of the key physicochemical quality elements that must be considered in order to have good ecological status.

The cumulative effects of global change, intense industrialization, agri-business, and increased population will intensify eutrophication in estuarine and coastal waters [4]. According to Abbiati et al. [5] climate change and human activities, such as aquaculture and agriculture, related to increased nutrient loadings are the main causes of hypoxia/anoxia, which is closely related to eutrophication and the resulting build-up of biomass with organic matter decomposition, which in turn leads to oxygen depletion. As stated by Rabalais et al. [6] hypoxia might exist naturally in many marine water bodies that are characterized by high productivity. However anthropogenic activities that are increasing the nutrient loading into the coastal water, resulted in the increase of frequency, magnitude, and extent of coastal hypoxia [7]. Hypoxia has an adverse effect on aquatic organisms (e.g., fish), which are depended on DO parameter for their efficient biological functioning [8]. According to Roman et al. [7] hypoxia is defined as coastal water having DO concentrations < 2 mg/l. However, some other marine water bodies have different thresholds for hypoxia. As stated by Schmidt et al. [9] estuarine waters have higher critical DO thresholds for hypoxia below 3mg/l.

Sensing technologies have been developed for water quality monitoring aiming to prevent/control hypoxia [10]. Furthermore, the employment of Artificial Intelligence techniques and specifically Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) for modelling the dynamics of DO parameter, is a reliable way for hypoxia process modelling. ANN's produce better modelling results in comparison with other data-driven models, like linear regression methods and decision trees, since these methodologies do not perform well when the data sample is small or does not follow certain assumptions about linear or Gaussian distributions [11]. On the other hand, ANNs are not impacted by the non-linearity effect that is frequently observed among environmental parameters. Several modelling studies using ANNs for predicting the DO levels exist.

In this study, we have utilized an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) as a modelling tool to predict the DO values for the coastal waters of Cyprus, because relevant DO modelling studies based on ANNs (e.g., Basant et al. [12]; Chen and Liu [13]; Xiao et al. [14]; Ziyat Sami et al. [15]) produced good outputs. Measurements from selected sampling stations of specific interest around the coastline of Cyprus (e.g., aquaculture stations, tourist areas, industrial areas, ecological sensitive areas) were used for training and validating the model. Moreover, a sensitivity analysis was conducted to identify the most influential parameters related with DO dynamics. The created ANN is a regional model, taking into consideration the unique environmental characteristics of Cyprus coastal water quality parameters and produce highly accurate results, based on which several management scenarios (mainly related with nutrients control) can be investigated and by that way to become a useful management tool.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study Area and Monitored Data

The Republic of Cyprus is an island located in the Levantine Basin (Eastern Mediterranean), which is one of the most oligotrophic seas in the world, characterized by very low nutrient availability and very low primary production [16]. High mean surface water temperatures prevailed in the Levant's Sea, ranging yearly from 16 °C in the winter up to 26 °C in the summer period. Moreover, the inflow of fresh water is very limited due to the lack of large rivers [17] and extensive damming in the area [18]. Additionally, the salinity and evaporation are high, since the average salinity of coastal waters of Cyprus is 39.1 psu., while the yearly average salinity of Eastern Mediterranean is about 37.5 psu.

The used data set contains measurements of surface environmental parameters obtained from 49 coastal stations near Cyprus (Figure 1), with different anthropogenic impact/activities (aquaculture, nearby industrial units), as monitored by the Department of Fisheries and Marine Research (DFMR) of the Cyprus Republic. The data considered for this study includes 1552 measurements collected sporadically (no regular time intervals) from several sampling stations (see Figure 1) between the years 2000-2021.

Figure 1. Combined satellite maps of Eastern Mediterranean Sea and Cyprus Island. The sampling stations from several areas near Cyprus coastline are marked with green colour.

The monitored environmental parameters were the following: nitrogen species (NH_4^+ , NO_2^- , NO_3^-); ortho-phosphates (PO_4^{3-}); salinity; DO; pH; electrical conductivity (EC); water temperature (WT); and Chl-*a*. The basic statistical properties of each monitored parameter are summarized based on the associated boxplot (see Figure 2). More details regarding the stations and the data sampling process can be found in the technical report by Antoniadis et al. [17].

Figure 2. Illustration of the box plot analysis of the measured environmental parameters. The red marks represent the outliers/extreme values; the red horizontal line represents the median value; the box gives the 25–75% percentile; the whiskers represent the data valid range.

2.2. Artificial Neural Networks Basics

ANNs are data-driven models with the ability to perform well even on large-scale complex data sets [19]. The feed-forward multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) utilizing the back-propagation training algorithm is a popular ANN for marine studies [20]. Theoretically any continuous function can be approximated by a feed-forward neural network with one hidden layer [21].

A feedforward ANN has its nodes (neurons) arranged on at least three layers (the input layer, the hidden layer/s and the output layer) and synaptic weights connect each node with all the nodes of the next layer. The output is calculated by applying the transfer function on the aggregated result of the weighted inputs [22] (which are associated with the previous ANN's layer). The procedure to calculate the output value of the j^{th} node (o_j) is found in the study of Dedecker et al. [23] and is synopsized based on the following mathematical formulas:

$$o_j = g(u_j) \quad (1)$$

$$u_j = \sum_{i=1}^j w_{ij} p_i + b_j \quad (2)$$

Where the term g is symbolizing the transfer function, p_i symbolizes the input from i^{th} node belonging to the previous layer, the term w_{ij} symbolizes the synaptic weight that connects the input (p_i) with the j^{th} node and b_j symbolizes a bias term. The ANN's training is repeated several times and each time the synaptic weights are changing in order the error between the real data and the calculated data to be small enough [24].

The number of ANN's hidden nodes is depended by the given data set, while some heuristic rules (for more details please see the study of Goethals et al. [25]) or the trial-and-error procedure [26] are recommended. Generally, the ANN might overfit the unknown data when it has too many nodes in the hidden layer [27, 28], and the training time might be very long [29].

The Garson's algorithm (or else the "Weights" sensitivity analysis algorithm) calculates the impact of each ANN's input to the ANN's output [30, 31]. The relative parameter importance (PI) is described by following mathematical formula [31]:

$$PI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{nL} \sum_{j=1}^{nK} |(w_{ij})|}{\sum_{k=1}^{nP} (\sum_{i=1}^{nL} \sum_{j=1}^{nK} |(w_{ij})|)_k} \quad (3)$$

Where the term nL symbolizes the time lagging number, the term nK symbolizes the number of hidden neurons and the term nP symbolizes the number of input parameters. Statistical criteria like the Root mean square error ($RMSE$) and the Coefficient of determination (R^2) are used as ANN's performance indices for evaluating the ANN's results (for test set data). The mathematical formulas describing these performance indices are given as below respectively:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (o_i - c_i)^2}{N}} \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (o_i - o)^2 - \sum_{i=1}^N (o_i - c_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (o_i - o)^2} \quad (5)$$

where o_i is the measured value; o is the average measured value; c_i the calculated value and N the number of data measurements.

2.3. Artificial Neural Network Development

The ANN's candidate input parameters were the pH, WT, EC, salinity, Chl-a., NH_4^+ , NO_2^- , NO_3^- and PO_4^{3-} , while the output was the DO parameter. The monitored parameters were examined for collinearity

using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), but no strong correlation existed ($r < 0.70$); therefore, all the monitored parameters were used as ANN's model inputs. This is a widely used procedure to help reducing the number of ANN's inputs and consequently, the model's complexity [32]. The MATLAB software was used for the ANN's development and data analysis.

The data set's missing values were linearly interpolated because a significant proportion of data (about 15 %) were missing values. This procedure helped the created ANN to produce better outputs, since the ANN was trained on a bigger data set resulted from interpolation. All the data were first normalized (min-max normalization) prior to applying to the ANN model, to avoid model bias [33].

An ANN with a 9-5-1 topology (based on the form $L1-H1-L2$, where $L1$ is the number of neurons in the input layer, $H1$ the number of neurons in the hidden layer and $L2$ the number of neurons in output layer) was used for the needs of this modelling study, since it produced the best results among several other tested-candidate topologies following the trial-and-error procedure. The sigmoid transfer function was used as the activation function between the input and hidden layer.

The regularization method was utilized to ensure that the model will not overfit the data [34]. Based on this method, the data set consisting of $n=1552$ samples was divided into two subsets, the training set ($n1=1242$) containing 80% of the data and the test set ($n2=310$) containing the remaining 20% of the data. The Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) algorithm was used as the ANN's training algorithm, because it exhibits fast learning speed and has demonstrated the best performance for training among the other tested variations of back-propagation algorithms for medium-sized networks [35].

3. Results

The performance indices of the proposed ANN's test set are given by $RMSE=0.0534$ and $R^2=0.991$. From both of these indices, it becomes apparent that the created ANN is a reliable predictor and can simulate the DO levels with good accuracy. As stated by Gazzaz et al. [36] when the created ANN model, has low RMSE and R^2 value close to 1, then it is considered an optimal predictor. For the implemented ANN model, the illustration of the real data points against the simulated data is graphically represented in Figure 3. It is clearly observed that the real data are in good agreement with the predicted DO values.

Figure 3. Graphical representation of the monitored (real) dissolved oxygen (DO) values against the ANN model predicted values

Sensitivity analysis was performed by applying the “Weights” method. The results of the sensitivity analysis are graphically illustrated in Figure 4, where the impact/contribution of each input environmental parameter on the DO parameter is calculated. It is clearly observed that the most contributing parameter is the WT (22.42%); followed by EC (18.00%). The rest of the parameters are much less contributing in the following order: pH (11.84%), salinity (9.95%), NH_4 (8.93%), NO_3 (8.28%), NO_2 (6.98%), Chl-a (6.89%) and PO_4 (6.70%).

Figure 4. The sensitivity analysis calculating ANN's input parameters contribution (%) based on the "Weights" algorithm. Where the ANN's input parameters: electric conductivity (EC); pH; salinity (sal); water temperature (WT); chlorophyll-a (Chl-a); ammonium (NH₄); nitrite (NO₂); nitrate (NO₃) and phosphate (PO₄).

4. Discussion

ANN models were utilized in this modelling study for simulating coastal DO levels, because of their ability to model complex non-linear systems, like the DO dynamics. Furthermore, ANNs are considered an advanced modelling technique, because they can be used on a heterogeneous data set and they require no *a priori* assumptions about the model or the data distribution [37], recalling that heterogeneity is a characteristic of the data set used in this modelling study. The adaptation of ANNs for water quality studies is considered a good modelling practice, since ANNs are capable of producing good outputs, when other modelling techniques might fail [1]. Indeed, the created ANN model managed to predict the DO levels with accuracy and is considered a reliable predictor for the DO parameter.

The sensitivity analysis calculated that the WT parameter is the most influential input parameter for the simulated DO. This ANN's finding is verified by the study of Schmidt et al [9], where Bordeaux waters were examined and it was found that the temperature was the main control factor of the DO variability, having a negative correlation $r=-0.85$. These findings are also in agreement with the study of Rivaro et al. [38], which examined the spatial and seasonal variability of DO and nutrients in the Southern Adriatic coastal waters. This study observed that the spatial distribution of DO had the highest surface levels recorded in March in most coastal stations, while temperature and salinity were lower than in the offshore stations. In another study of Alkhalidi et al. [39], Statistical Analysis was applied in order to investigate the relationships between coastal water parameters; and it confirmed the negative relationship between high WT and low DO levels, which were associated with the fish kill events that occurred during April and May 2017 in the Kuwait bay.

The EC was calculated to be the second most contributing parameter to the simulated DO. This ANN's finding might be attributed to the fact that elevated values of EC are correlated with an increase of nutrient levels into the water column and therefore resulting into increased algal production [33], which is associated with hypoxia and low DO levels. Hence, based on this indirect relationship the EC and DO parameters can be related. Similarly, an indirect relationship between the pH parameter and DO exists, since according to the study of Ferreira et al [40], there is an association between slightly more alkaline conditions and marine eutrophication and the possible hypoxia. Based on the ANN's sensitivity analysis results the salinity parameter is having a moderate impact on the simulated DO. As recorded in the study of Rivaro et al. [38] the salinity resulted in an inverse correlation to oxygen, while high values of DO are related with low values of nutrients. According to Fahmy [41], even though there is no "cause-effect" relationship among physical and chemical coastal variables, the correlation analysis is a sufficient way to understand the underlying parameters/factors related to the productivity of the Red Sea coastal waters, such as salinity, water temperature and DO.

The need to monitor/record reliable observations related to DO is emphasized by Schmidt et al. [9], for a better understanding of the dynamics of DO and how they interact with climate pressures (e.g., climate change, salinization) and local pressures (e.g., wastewater influences), since this is necessary for proper management of hypoxia. In the future, we plan to enhance and recalibrate the current ANN with denser measurements coming from other available sources (e.g., satellite data), as well as additional variables (e.g., rainfall, sandstorms), so as to become a powerful management tool, capable to forecast

ahead possible hypoxic events and investigate specialized/customised modelling scenarios focusing on aquaculture units well-functioning.

5. Conclusions

Predicting DO levels is a crucial task for water quality management, especially in areas where aquaculture units are operating, in order to ensure that no hypoxic events will affect the unit's proper operation. Based on the created ANN model specific environmental conditions, such as a combination of high nutrients concentration and elevated water temperature can be used as model's inputs, to predict the associated DO output value. Therefore, several management scenarios can be examined for calculating the nutrients thresholds in accordance with the mean monthly/seasonal tendency of the rest of the environmental parameters and especially the water temperature parameter. Based on the "Weights" sensitivity analysis algorithm it was calculated that the water temperature is the most contributing input parameter on the DO process, highlighting the impact of elevated temperatures and the global warming phenomenon on coastal hypoxia.

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